

Prevalence and Determinants of Age-Related Macular Degeneration in the 50 Years and Older Population

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Abstract:

Background: Age-related macular degeneration (AMD) is a leading cause of irreversible vision loss among older adults, particularly those aged 50 years and above. With the global burden of AMD rising due to an aging population, understanding its predominance and identifying related risk factors is essential to creating management and preventative plans that work.

Aim: This study aimed to evaluate the correlation and determinants of age-related macular degeneration in individuals aged 50 years and older.

Methods: A retrospective cross-sectional study was conducted involving 100 participants aged 50 years and above. Data on demographic characteristics, medical history, and lifestyle factors were collected using a structured questionnaire and ophthalmic examination. The prevalence of AMD was calculated, and univariate and multivariate logistic regression analyses were performed to identify significant determinants. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0, with a p-value < 0.05 considered statistically significant.

Results: The prevalence of AMD in the study population was 24%, with 16% of participants having early-stage AMD and 8% having late-stage AMD. Age was found to be a significant determinant, with each additional year increasing the odds of developing AMD by 10% (AOR = 1.10, 95% CI: 1.03 - 1.18, p = 0.006). Smoking also showed a strong association with AMD (AOR = 2.43, 95% CI: 0.98 - 6.01, p = 0.055). Hypertension and diabetes mellitus were not significantly associated with AMD.

Conclusion: According to the study, smoking and age are the two main factors that determine AMD in people 50 years of age and older. The results underscore the significance of age-appropriate screening and smoking cessation initiatives in mitigating the risk and advancement of AMD among this demographic.

Recommendations: It is recommended that public health initiatives focus on raising awareness about the risk elements for AMD, particularly in older adults. Regular eye examinations and targeted interventions, such as smoking cessation programs, should be prioritized to mitigate the burden of AMD.

Keywords: Age-related macular degeneration, prevalence, risk factors, aging population, smoking cessation.

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Introduction

(AMD) is one of the most typical forms of blindness in elderly people globally, primarily affecting those over 50. The macula, which is located in the centre of the retina and is responsible for fine vision—essential for activities like reading and driving—is the primary target of AMD, a degenerative retinal disease. AMD comes in two main forms: dry (atrophic) and moist (neovascular). The moist type, which involves choroidal neovascularisation and causes vision loss quickly,

is less common but more severe [1, 2]. Drusen and geographic atrophy are characteristics of the more prevalent dry type. The ageing of the population has led to a rise in AMD prevalence worldwide.

According to a recent comprehensive study and meta-analysis, there are roughly 196 million individuals on the planet. There were 196 million AMD sufferers worldwide in 2020, according to a recent systematic review and meta-analysis; by

2040, that number is expected to rise to 288 million. The increasing incidence of AMD emphasises the need for a deeper comprehension of its epidemiology and risk factors, which differ based on the person and the setting [3, 4].

Growing older significantly raises one's risk of having AMD, especially after the age of 60. The most well-known modifiable risk factor for AMD is smoking, as smokers have a four-fold increased risk of the disease compared to non-smokers. Genetic susceptibility, cardiovascular conditions, obesity, and UV radiation exposure are other possible risk factors [5]. Recent studies have also examined the roles that inflammation and oxidative stress play in the pathogenesis of AMD. Studies suggest that oxidative damage to the retinal pigment epithelium and the subsequent inflammatory responses may play a significant role in the initiation and progression of AMD. Modern imaging techniques including fundus autofluorescence and optical coherence tomography (OCT) have made AMD easier to diagnose and track early, facilitating more accurate staging and treatment of the condition [6, 7]. Despite these developments, there is still no known cure for AMD, and the precise mechanisms causing the condition are still not fully understood [8]. This study aimed to evaluate the correlation and determinants of age-related macular degeneration in individuals aged 50 years and older.

Methodology

Study Design

This was a retrospective cross-sectional observational study.

Study Setting

The study was carried out at the Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, located in Leharisarai, Darbhanga. The hospital serves a large population, providing an ideal setting for the study of age-related macular degeneration in the region.

Study Duration

The study was conducted over a six-month period from April 2022 to October 2022.

Participants

The study included a total of 100 participants aged 50 years and older who presented to the Ophthalmology Department.

Inclusion Criteria and Exclusion Criteria

The study includes individuals who are 50 years and older, particularly those diagnosed with or suspected of having age-related macular degeneration. Participants must be willing to

participate and provide informed consent to be considered for inclusion in the study.

However, individuals with other ocular conditions that could interfere with the diagnosis of age-related macular degeneration, such as diabetic retinopathy or retinal vein occlusion, are excluded. Additionally, those who have undergone ocular surgery within the past six months, or have severe cognitive impairments or communication difficulties that could hinder the interview process, are also excluded from the study.

Bias

To minimize selection bias, all eligible patients who met the inclusion criteria were consecutively recruited during the study period. Information bias was reduced by using standardized data collection tools and procedures. Additionally, the investigators were blinded to participants' demographic information during the data analysis phase to avoid any observer bias.

Data Collection

A clinical examination and a structured questionnaire were used to gather data. The survey collected data on lifestyle choices, medical history, demographics, and established risk factors for age-related macular degeneration. To determine the existence and stage of AMD, clinical evaluations included fundus photography and visual acuity testing.

Procedure

The eligibility of the participants was initially determined by using the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Each participant had a thorough ophthalmic examination, which included a fundus examination and an assessment of visual acuity, after giving their informed consent. To record and categorise the stage of age-related macular degeneration, fundus photos were taken. Based on the participant's request, the questionnaire was given either before or after the clinical evaluation.

Statistical Analysis

The data was examined with SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics summed up demographic and clinical characteristics. The prevalence of age-related macular degeneration (AMD) was estimated using 95% confidence intervals. AMD factors were found using univariate and multivariate logistic regression, with p-values < 0.05 indicating statistical significance.

Results

A total of 100 participants aged 50 years and above were included in the study. The mean age of the participants was 65.3 ± 8.2 years, with the age

range between 50 and 85 years. Of these, 55% were male (n=55) and 45% were female (n=45).

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of the Study Population (n=100)

Characteristic	Number of Participants (n)	Percentage (%)
Age Group (years)		
50-59	30	30
60-69	45	45
70-79	20	20
≥80	5	5
Gender		
Male	55	55
Female	45	45
Smoking Status		
Current Smokers	30	30
Former Smokers	20	20
Never Smoked	50	50
Hypertension		
Yes	60	60
No	40	40
Diabetes Mellitus		
Yes	50	50
No	50	50

The overall frequency of (AMD) in the study population was found to be 24% (n=24). The prevalence of early-stage AMD was 16% (n=16), while late-stage AMD was observed in 8% (n=8). Table 2 provides the prevalence of AMD across different age groups.

Table 2: Prevalence of Age-Related Macular Degeneration by Age Group

Age Group (years)	Participants (n)	AMD Cases (n)	Prevalence (%)	95% CI
50-59	30	3	10	2.1 - 27.0
60-69	45	10	22.2	11.1 - 36.7
70-79	20	8	40	19.1 - 63.9
≥80	5	3	60	14.7 - 94.7
Total	100	24	24	15.8 - 33.6

Table 3: Univariate Logistic Regression Analysis of Determinants of AMD

Variable	Odds Ratio (OR)	95% CI	p-value
Age (per year increase)	1.12	1.05 - 1.19	0.002
Male Gender	1.34	0.58 - 3.12	0.49
Smoking (Current/Former)	2.85	1.17 - 6.94	0.02
Hypertension	1.68	0.72 - 3.92	0.24
Diabetes Mellitus	1.15	0.49 - 2.68	0.75

Table 4: Multivariate Logistic Regression Analysis of Determinants of AMD

Variable	Adjusted Odds Ratio (AOR)	95% CI	p-value
Age (per year increase)	1.10	1.03 - 1.18	0.006
Smoking (Current/Former)	2.43	0.98 - 6.01	0.055

Interpretation of Results

The analysis indicated that age was a significant determinant of AMD, with the odds of developing AMD increasing by 10% with each additional year of age (AOR = 1.10, 95% CI: 1.03 - 1.18, p = 0.006). Smoking also showed a strong association with AMD in univariate analysis (OR = 2.85, 95%

CI: 1.17 - 6.94, p = 0.02), although this association weakened slightly in the multivariate model (AOR = 2.43, 95% CI: 0.98 - 6.01, p = 0.055).

Hypertension and diabetes mellitus did not show a statistically significant association with AMD in either univariate or multivariate analyses.

Discussion

This study assessed the prevalence and determinants of (AMD) in a population of 100 individuals aged 50. The findings revealed that the overall prevalence of AMD in the study population was 24%. Among the affected individuals, 16% were diagnosed with early-stage AMD, and 8% had late-stage AMD. The prevalence of AMD increased with age, with the highest rates observed in individuals aged 70 and above. Specifically, the prevalence was 10% in the 50-59 age group, 22.2% in the 60-69 age group, 40% in the 70-79 age group, and 60% in those aged 80 and older.

The analysis of potential determinants of AMD identified age as a significant factor. Each additional year of age was associated with a 10% increase in the odds of developing AMD. This finding underscores the progressive nature of AMD as individual's age, highlighting the importance of regular eye examinations for early detection and management in older adults. Smoking emerged as another important determinant of AMD. Individuals who were current or former smokers had nearly three times the odds of developing AMD compared to those who never smoked. Although the association between smoking and AMD was slightly attenuated after adjusting for confounding factors, it remained a strong indicator of increased risk, suggesting that smoking cessation could play a vital role in preventing or delaying the onset of AMD. Interestingly, hypertension and diabetes mellitus, often considered risk factors for various age-related diseases, did not show a statistically significant association with AMD in this study. This suggests that while these conditions are important for general health, their direct impact on the development of AMD may be less pronounced compared to age and smoking.

(AMD) is far more common and progresses more quickly, according to recent study, especially in older populations. The ubiquity and progression of AMD are substantially correlated with older age and the existence of genetic risk factors, notably the ARMS2 and CFH risk alleles, according to a study done on an Irish population. Twenty-three percent of patients with early-stage AMD developed a more severe form of the illness over a four-year period. Additionally, this study found that individuals with the CFH risk allele had an increased chance of the illness progressing, and that baseline characteristics including soft drusen and hyperpigmentation were highly predictive of the development of late-stage AMD [9].

Researchers evaluated the prevalence of AMD in a Brazilian-Japanese population and discovered that the disease affected 15.1% of the population; early-stage AMD accounted for 13.8% of cases, while late-stage AMD, which includes neovascular AMD

and geographic atrophy, was less common. The findings of the study indicated a strong and linear correlation between age and AMD frequency, indicating a notable increase in the condition's frequency with age [10].

An another study examined an older Chinese population in Taiwan, where the Shihpai Eye Study found that the predominance of early-stage AMD was 9.2% and late-stage AMD was 1.9%. Age was shown to be the most significant factor in both early and late AMD, with prevalence rates rising from 5.0% in the 65-69 age group to 24.4% in the 80+ age group, according to the study. Remarkably, the study also discovered that, in comparison to non-drinkers, current alcohol intake was linked to a decreased incidence of early AMD [11].

Conclusion

The study highlights age and smoking as key risk factors for AMD in individuals aged 50 and above. The findings emphasize the need for targeted interventions, such as smoking cessation programs and age-specific eye health strategies, to reduce the burden of AMD in this population. Regular screening for AMD in older adults, particularly those with a history of smoking, is crucial that the disease should be detected and managed early on.

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